

28 °C, after which they were kept in a humid room with an automatic mister at the same temperature for 12 d before the disease was assessed.

This method requires only a small amount of spore suspension (1×10^5 conidia/ml) and gives a panicle infection frequency of nearly 100%.

Smear inoculation produces a higher BI score and BI index than spray inoculation, but lower than injection inoculation (see table).

The new method is suitable for inoculation at 0-10 d after heading, but is especially suitable at 0-3 d after heading (see figure). □

Comparison of inoculation methods to induce neck BI in rice panicles in vitro. Hangzhou, China, 1990.

Variety	Infection frequency (%)			BI score ^a			BI index ^b		
	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying
<i>Panicles in vitro</i>									
Jiannongzao 9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Zhe 852	12.5	10.0	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.0	5.0	3.2	0.0
Erjiufeng	100.0	100.0	60.0	6.5	6.1	2.5	72.0	68.0	28.0
Zhefu 802	100.0	100.0	80.0	8.3	6.1	5.8	92.0	68.0	64.0
Yuanfengzao	100.0	100.0	100.0	9.0	5.4	6.8	100.0	60.0	76.0
Guangluai 4	100.0	100.0	100.0	9.0	7.9	6.5	100.0	88.0	72.0
<i>Panicles in vivo</i>									
Jiannongzao 9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Zhe 852	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Erjiufeng	100.0	85.7	18.2	7.2	2.3	0.4	80.0	25.7	6.2
Zhefu 802	88.9	72.7	66.7	5.2	3.6	4.5	57.8	40.0	49.3
Yuanfengzao	100.0	84.7	70.0	8.3	5.4	4.5	92.5	60.0	50.0
Guangluai 4	100.0	92.9	72.7	9.0	7.2	5.0	100.0	80.0	56.4

^a Based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

^b Disease index = $\frac{\sum (\text{no. of panicles with a given score} \times \text{value of that score})}{\text{total no. of panicles} \times \text{value of the highest score}}$

Effect of plant extracts on in vitro growth of rice blast (BI) pathogen *Piricularia oryzae*

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We tested 15 plant extracts for their effect on the growth of BI pathogen *P. oryzae*. Filtrates were taken as either a cold water or a hot water extract. For the cold water extract, fresh leaves were ground in sterile distilled water at 1:1 wt/vol with mortar and pestle and strained through a muslin cloth. For the hot water extract, leaves were immersed in water at 1:1 wt/vol, heated to 80 °C for 10 minutes, and then ground with a mortar and pestle.

To prepare the ethanol extract, we ground 100 g of leaf material in 100 ml of 95% ethanol. The homogenate was filtered through muslin cloth and the filtrate was evaporated at laboratory temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). The residue was then dissolved in 100 ml of sterile distilled water.

The three extracts were heated separately to 45-50 °C for 10 minutes to eliminate contamination. Another cold water extract, prepared as described above, was also autoclaved at 20 lb pressure. We then added 2 ml of the four preparations to 18 ml of apple agar

medium in sterile petri dishes, and spread the extracts on the agar surface by rotation. With a sterile cork borer, we punched an 8-mm fungal disc from a 7-d-old culture of *P. oryzae*. The disc was placed in the middle of the petri dishes. The dishes were incubated at room temperature ($28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Control treatments contained only inoculated apple agar medium. When the fungal growth in control dishes touched the periphery 12 d later, we measured the diameter of the colony for the respective treatments.

To assess biomass production, we added 8-mm fungal discs to flasks containing Richard's broth and 5 ml of the cold water extract of the plants. The

control contained only broth. We obtained the biomass 10 d after incubation at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ by filtering the medium through Whatman no. 1 filter paper. The biomass was dried at 105 °C in a hot air oven for 48 h and then kept in a desiccator until constant weight was obtained.

Radial growth and biomass production were significantly reduced by extracts of all 15 plant species tested (see table). Cold water, hot water, and ethanol extracts inhibited the fungus better than the autoclaved extracts did. *Prosopis juliflora*, *Adhatoda vasica*, and *Vitex negundo*, which are commonly available on farms, showed the maximum inhibition. □

Effect of plant extracts on the growth of *P. oryzae*.^a

Plant species	Inhibition of radial growth ^a compared with control				
	Cold water extract	Hot water extract	Ethanol extract	Extract autoclaved	Biomass production
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	87.4 b	80.3 a	89.1 b	65.1 a	89.7 b
<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	35.0 h	28.4 f	34.5 h	20.4 e	42.5 h
<i>Antigonon leptopus</i>	4.8 i	3.7 h	3.6 k	2.4 g	4.1 i
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	66.5 d	61.6 b	71.5 c	60.2 ab	60.8 d
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	6.1 i	6.2 g	7.3 ij	4.8 g	5.7 i
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	46.1 f	43.6 de	47.3 fg	22.8 de	45.9 g
<i>Datura metel</i>	5.5	4.9 gh	9.6 i	8.6 f	6.0 i
<i>Ipomea carnea</i>	46.8 f	40.4 e	43.0 g	27.2 d	41.6 h
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	48.1 f	49.3 c	52.1 e	47.1 e	47.3 g
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	40.3 g	46.1 cd	49.6 ef	42.8 c	51.9 f
<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i>	53.3 e	43.5 de	47.9 efg	48.4 c	46.6 g
<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	64.5 d	44.1 de	68.4 d	55.8 b	55.2 e
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	93.3 a	78.5 a	92.1 a	62.7 a	100.0 a
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	4.2 i	3.0 h	6.7 j	4.2 g	5.4 i
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	72.4 c	64.5 b	73.3 c	55.2 h	71.4 c

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b In a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.